

DETERMINING THE DYNAMICS OF GENERAL PHYSICAL FITNESS OF HIGHLY SKILLED FOOTBALL GIRLS

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Abstract: In this article, the movement preparation (speed, endurance, agility, technique) of highly skilled football players engaged in the pre-competition training period is researched based on the players' playing roles and individual characteristics. At the same time, the results of sports training of female football players participating in Navbahor-W (Namangan city) and AGMK-W (Almalik city) teams were comparatively analyzed.

Keywords: highly qualified players, functional training, quickness, endurance, agility, training planning, control exercises, general physical training, role, dynamics.

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ДИНАМИКИ ОБЩЕЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВЛЕННОСТИ ВЫСОКОКВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ДЕВУШЕК-ФУТБОЛИСТОК

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется двигательная активность (скорость, выносливость, ловкость, техничность) высококвалифицированных шахматисток в период предтурнирной подготовки на основе игровой ампулы и индивидуальных особенностей участниц. При этом был проведен сравнительный анализ тренировочной готовности игроков-женщин команд «Навбахор-Ж» и «АГМК-Ж».

Ключевые слова: игроки высокой квалификации, функциональная подготовка, ловкость, выносливость, ловкость, планирование тренировки, контрольные упражнения, общая физическая подготовка, динамика.

INTRODUCTION

Football the most popular sport among the population in Uzbekistan, to establish a system for selecting and selecting highly talented young players and training them as professional athletes, to bring the country's football to a level where it can compete with developed countries, to train football specialists based on international requirements and standards, development of football clubs, effective organization of training processes for national teams, holding major international football competitions in our country, including world and continental championships among youth, youth and women's teams. Decree No. PF-5887 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 4, 2019 "On measures to bring the development of football to a completely new level in Uzbekistan", March 16, 2018 "Measures for the further development of football" "On events" and decrees No. PQ-3610 indicate that the attention paid to football in our country, especially to women's sports, is at a high level [1,2].

In recent years, efforts to ensure gender equality and increase the role of women in social and political life have been carried out in several directions:

- Improvement of legislation on women's rights;
- Improvement of the institutional foundations of women's protection;
- raising awareness of the population about gender equality and women's rights;

- train officials responsible for ensuring their compliance in law enforcement practice on the basis of relevant legal norms.

Uzbekistan has adopted a number of legal documents, including presidential decrees and decisions on ensuring women's rights, in particular, on gender equality and protecting women from violence and oppression, strengthening the status of women's entrepreneurship development.

It is necessary to emphasize the positive changes in education from the point of view of introducing gender equality. That is, since 2017, the activity of part-time departments in various specialties has been restored in higher educational institutions. This form of education allows young women to obtain higher education without compromising childcare and other family responsibilities [3].

As we know from the theory and practice of football, the training of highly qualified football players is a process with its own characteristics. A number of scientists, including: P.P. Viktorovich [2020] general and special training according to the pre-season functional training program of highly qualified football players, according to annual training cycles, [4; 7-8 b], D.V. Viprikov [2008] applied the training loads to different stages of the training period in order to comprehensively evaluate the training loads of qualified futsal players, [5; 6-7 b], A.Stula, G.Vladimir [2015] on specialized, extended and long-term planning stages of training load planning and management in football, [6; 36. b], E.I.Ivanchenko [2019] the general structure of the training process for planning sports training and the specific characteristics of the dynamics of the athletes' working ability, work of different nature and direction during training described its distribution in detail [7; 19-20 b], N.M. Yusupov conducted research on methods of development of quick-strength training of highly skilled football players [8; 36 b]. However, we can see that the menstrual period has not been sufficiently studied in the scientific research conducted in high-quality football players.

To date, in order to properly organize the training process of highly qualified football players, in order to properly organize the training process during the menstrual period, the normalization of the loads taking into account the external environmental conditions of the athletes in the stage of general and special physical and technical training is part of our research work. determined its relevance.

The purpose of the research: to determine the dynamics of movement training of highly qualified football players during the pre-competition training period.

Research tasks: to determine the characteristics of the movement readiness of highly skilled soccer girls;

mutual comparative analysis of the dynamics of movement preparation of highly skilled football players;

analysis of highly qualified football players, taking into account the game role of girls;

RESEARCH METHODS

Scientific methodical literature analysis, pedagogical observation, interview, pedagogical test, mathematical statistical methods were used.

The object of research: the training process of highly skilled soccer girls.

Research subject: means and methods of development of pre-competition training of football players.

Organization of the research: experiment Pedagogical experiment was conducted during the period from 2020 to 2021. This experiment was carried out in the process of determining the general

physical and technical conditions of highly qualified football players playing in the "Navbahor-W" (Namangan city) and "AGMK-W" (Almalik city) teams of the higher league.

20 female players took part in the experiment (8 defenders, 8 midfielders, 4 forwards).

A characteristic feature of modern football is the high level of activity of the players in relation to the actions and non-rhythmic (arrhythmic) description of the work performed. Running occupies the largest place in activities related to movements. In this case, the speed of running varies from slow to maximum. Speed is important in football - a player with a good level of speed will obviously have an advantage over his opponent in occupying space and gaining time, which means that in this case he can successfully solve the tactical task set before him. . In football, speed is not only the speed of running over a distance, but also the speed of thinking, the speed of working with the ball [9; 168-169. b].

In order to determine and monitor the level of general physical and technical training of highly skilled football players, a comparative statistical analysis of the speed, agility, endurance qualities and technical training ability of AGMK-W and Navbahor-W team football players was conducted (1 -see table).

High-skilled football players set 30 m for girls. It was found that the defenders of the Navbahor-W team had an average of 5.14 seconds in running from a high start. We can see that AGMK-W's defenders have a speed index of 4.94 seconds, and compared to Navbahor-W's team, AGMK-W's team showed a better result by 0.15 seconds. It is recommended to give loads taking into account the menstrual period in the development of the quality of quickness during the training of highly qualified football players.

Endurance is a person's ability to perform any activity for a long time without reducing its effectiveness. Due to the fact that the duration of work is ultimately limited by fatigue, endurance can also be expressed as the body's ability to withstand fatigue. Fatigue is a condition characterized by a decrease in the body's ability to work as a result of long-term heavy activity. It appears after a certain period of time after the start of the work and is manifested in the inability to perform the activity with the previous efficiency.

4x10 m from female football players on the development of endurance qualities. If we pay attention to the results of the shuttle run, it was found that Navbahor-W team defenders reached 10.67 seconds, and AGMK-W team defenders reached 10.37 seconds, and the difference between them and Navbahor-W team is 0.29 seconds.

The importance of the quality of agility, the coordination complexity of movements is the first measure of agility. If the space, time, force characteristics of the movement correspond to the task of the movement, the movement is sufficiently accurate, the tasks of the movement give rise to the concept of precision of the movement [9; 123.b].

According to the next indicator, 30 m. the quality of agility in running forward with the ball to a distance was determined by the following test. 30 m in this practice test. We can see that the defenders of the Navbahor-W team reached the distance in 6.06 seconds and the defenders of the AGMK-W team reached the distance in 6.08 seconds. Moving forward with the ball 30 m. we can see that Navbahor-W national team member's agility quality is 0.1 second better than AGMK-W national team defenders in distance running (See Figure 1).

1-tableAnalyzing the general physical fitness dynamics of highly skilled football players (n=20)

S.N.P	Ampula		30 m. high start running (s)	Mokisimon running 4x10 m. (s)	Fast forward with the ball. 30 m. (s)	30 m. taking the ball between the chips and hitting the goal from 16 yards (s)	Kicking the ball along a long corridor (m)		Ball play (junker) count
							right	left	
M-va M	protection	N-W	4,86	10,90	6,40	7,21	22	19	26
I-va G		A-W	4,71	10,16	6,55	7,06	24	33	39
A-va M	protection	N-W	5,29	10,76	5,85	5,10	20	32	179
U-va R		A-W	4,91	10,34	6,12	6,12	26	37	193
N-va Sh	protection	N-W	5,19	10,70	5,89	5,95	30	20	27
S-va J		A-W	4,84	10,48	6,08	5,47	26	34	87
M-va N	protection	N-W	5,22	10,34	6,13	6,83	29	14	63
N-va S		A-W	5,31	10,54	5,96	6,24	31	19	59
S-va R	midfield	N-W	4,64	10,82	6,12	6,56	24	11	26
Q-va S		A-W	4,50	10,38	5,68	6,42	28	17	98
D-va Ch	midfield	N-W	5,16	10,58	5,68	5,39	32	8	41
O-va A		A-W	4,82	9,90	5,76	5,18	29	27	69
K-va S	midfield	N-W	5,13	10,98	6,17	5,97	34	19	94
A-va L		A-W	5,41	10,64	6,24	5,84	21	26	87
K-va Sh	midfield	N-W	4,78	9,99	5,79	6,55	35	21	167
Q-va K		A-W	4,83	10,24	6,12	6,34	29	25	126
B-va Z	attack	N-W	4,72	10,34	5,64	5,74	16	33	184
O-va L		A-W	4,91	10,28	5,59	5,58	25	29	107
H-va G	attack	N-W	5,00	10,21	5,80	6,46	27	16	56
R-va L		A-W	4,75	10,58	5,24	5,14	31	23	98

Note: 1st control exercise: 30 metr high start running (s), 2nd control exercise: Mokisimon running 4x10 metr (s), 3rd control exercise: Fast forward with the ball. 30 metr. (s), 4th control exercise: 30 metr. taking the ball between the chips and hitting the goal from 16 yards (s).

30 m. carrying the ball between the chips to a distance of 16 m. according to the practical test performance of hitting the goal, the defenders of Navbahor-W took 6.27 seconds, and the members of the AGMK-W team took 6.22 seconds, and the difference between them was 0.05 seconds. The AGMK-W team had a good result it was found out.

Figure 1. Diagram showing the difference in general physical fitness dynamics of Narbakhor-W and AGMK-W team defenders

30 m according to the result of differentiating the defenders of the two teams in terms of general physical fitness. that the AGMK-W team showed a better result by 0.2 seconds and 4X10 m. by 0.29 seconds, 30 m according to the shuttle running practical test. 0.11 seconds according to the test of running with a ball, 30 m. carrying the ball between the chips to a distance of 16 m. We can see that AGMK-W's overall fitness level is better than that of Navbahor-W by 0.05 seconds in terms of shots on goal (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. Diagram showing the difference in general physical fitness dynamics of midfielders of Narbakhor-W and AGMK-W teams

Note: 1st control exercise: 30 metr high start running (s), 2nd control exercise: Mokisimon running 4x10 metr (s), 3rd control exercise: Fast forward with the ball. 30 metr. (s), 4th control exercise: 30 metr. taking the ball between the chips and hitting the goal from 16 yards (s).

Navbahor-W and AGMK-W team midfielders 0.03 seconds in 30m high start, 4x10m. 0.3 seconds on the shuttle run, 30 m. for 0.01 seconds in fast forward running with the ball, 30 m. carrying the ball between the chips to a distance of 16 m. It was found that the midfielders of the AGMK-W team showed a good result in hitting the goal by 0.17 seconds. Differences in general physical fitness of the midfielders of the two teams were examined (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Diagram showing the difference in general physical fitness dynamics of Narbakhor-W and AGMK-W strikers

Note: 1st control exercise: 30 metr high start running (s), 2nd control exercise: Mokisimon running 4x10 metr (s), 3rd control exercise: Fast forward with the ball. 30 metr. (s), 4th control exercise: 30 metr. taking the ball between the chips and hitting the goal from 16 yards (s).

If we pay attention to the test results obtained from the attackers of the Narbakhor-W and AGMK-W teams, the attackers of the Navbahor-W team are 30 m. 4x10 m. and in the shuttle run for 0.16 seconds, 30 m. for 0.31 seconds according to the practical test of running forward with a ball, 30 m. carrying the ball between the chips to a distance of 16 m. It was found that the strikers of the AGMK-W team had a better result than the strikers of the Navbahor-W team for 0.2 seconds in terms of hitting the goal (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. The diagram showing the difference in the dynamics of technical training of defenders of the Narbakhor-W and AGMK-W teams

Note: 1st-control exercise. kicking the ball far along the corridor (metr), 2st control exercise. Playing the ball (jungler).

We summarized the indicators of technical training of highly qualified soccer girls by using the following tests.

Defenders of Navbahor-W and AGMK-W team defenders of AGMK-W team are 11 m. we can see that they are better than their competitors.

It was found that the AGMK-W team had a good result in the practical test of playing ball (jungler) with 11 differences (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Diagram showing the difference in the dynamics of technical training of midfielders of the Narbakhor-W and AGMK-W teams

Note: 1st-control exercise. kicking the ball far along the corridor (metr), 2st control exercise. Playing the ball (jungler).

According to this practical test, the difference between Navbahor-W and AGMK-W team midfielders in terms of accurate delivery of the ball to a long distance along the corridor is 4.5 m. ga, playing the ball (jungler) with a difference of 11, the AGMK-W team proved to be a good result (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Diagram showing the difference in the dynamics of technical training of Narbakhor-W and AGMK-W strikers

Note: 1st-control exercise. kicking the ball far along the corridor (metr), 2st control exercise. Playing the ball (jungler).

According to the difference between Navbahor-W and AGMK-W team strikers in terms of technical training, the AGMK-W team is 8 m long in passing the ball along the corridor. ga, 18 on the ball play (jungler) test, the level of technical training of the AGMK-W team was determined to be good.

CONCLUSION

In the process of studying the scientific-methodical literature of foreign and local scientists, we came to the following conclusions based on the results of the analysis of scientific research on the training system of highly qualified female football players;

5-stage menstrual cycles have not been sufficiently investigated in the scientific research conducted on the physical and technical training of highly qualified football players;

- it was determined that the periods (menstrual, postmenstrual, ovulatory, postovulatory, premenstrual) should be taken into account when regulating the training loads of highly skilled football players, taking into account their role on the field;

- the correct organization of the 5-stage menstrual period for planning and regulating the intensity of loads during the training of highly skilled football players will have a positive effect.

Literature

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 4-dekabrdagi "O'zbekistonda futbolni rivojlantirishni mutlaqo yangi bosqichga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PF-5887-sonli farmoni. www. Lex.uz
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 16-martdagi "Futbolni yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" gi PQ 3610-sonli qarori. www. Lex.uz.
3. 2022-2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi Xelena FREYZER, Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining O'zbekistondagi doimiy vakili 2020 yil 8-yanvar.
4. 10. Abdullaev M.J Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (1-qism) Darslik Buxoro -2020. y.54-117-132.-b.
5. Стула А и Владимир Г Методология подготовки юных футболистов Книга. 2015. й.
6. Иванченко Е. И Основы планирования спортивной подготовки Пособие-Минск БГУФК 2019. й 19-20.-с.
7. Yusupov N.M Yuqori malakali futbolchi qizlarni tezkor-kuch tayyorgarligining rivojlantirish uslubini takomillashtirish. Dissertatsiya. Chirchiq 2018.y 126.-b.
8. Iseyev Sh.T. Futbolchilarni yillik siklda tayyorlashni rejalashtirish. O'quv qo'llanma Toshkent 2014. y. 460 b.
9. Викторovich В.Д Построение учебно-тренировочного процесса на основе комплексной оценки нагрузок квалифицированных спортсменов в мини-футболе. Автореферат-Малаховка 2008. й. 6.- с.
10. Викторovich П.П программа функциональной подготовки высококвалифицированных футболистов в процессе предсезонных сборов по системе «осень-весна» автореферат-москва 2020.й 7.- с.